

3rd wave survey - 2023

Finland

Age group

In 2023, the data collection involved a total of **1366 students**.

Gender distribution

SES distribution

On average, adolescents reported **knowing very well** how to do 69% of the activities on digital **communication and interaction**, but only 41% of the activities related to **information and navigation**.

On average, boys reported being on high level in 49% of **information and navigation** skills compared to girls who reported 35% of these skills at a high level.

The average of correct answers to digital knowledge is 62%. The percentage of correct answers related to digital knowledge is similar between boys and girls.

Knowledge items*

* Respondents answered a set of questions designed to measure their actual knowledge about how the internet and digital technologies work.

How digital literacy levels changed in adolescents who participated in three waves (441)?

Considering both the self-reported skills and knowledge items reported in the three waves, there are no statistical differences between the years in the three dimensions below. Less than half of the participants reported a high level of **digital literacy*** in **content creation** and **information and navigation**.

Communication and interaction

Content creation and production

Information and navigation

* **Digital literacy** is a combination of digital skills and knowledge regarding how the internet and digital technologies work.

The levels of digital literacy are a merger of self-reported high-level skills and the correct answer on the knowledge items. For technological and operational skills digital literacy could not be accounted for due to a lack of knowledge items.

In 2023, boys presented higher digital literacy levels than girls in **information and navigation** (55% to 43%). The students however reported no gender differences regarding **content creation and production** and **communication and interaction**.